

Dynamic Gratings for Contactless Material Diagnostics

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This paper demonstrates the potentialities of the dynamic gratings (spatial modulation spectroscopy) method using for nondestructive material diagnostics, separation of different nonlinearity mechanisms, measurements of thermo-optical and kinetic characteristics. Recording of short-lived (hundreds of microseconds) and long-lived (several seconds) gratings in photorefractive crystals of bismuth silicate have been studied. It has been established that a mechanism of the short-lived gratings is local whereas that of the long-lived gratings is nonlocal (diffusion). In the process of the surface transient gratings recording in samples of ZnGeP₂ single crystal the amplitude and phase components of a diffracted signal have been separated. It has been shown that attenuation of a signal from the amplitude grating is governed by the local-type relaxation processes (recombination of free carriers). In-plane thermal diffusivity has been measured; and it has been found that there is no anisotropy of thermal diffusivity for different orientations of the thermal grating vector with respect to the crystal axis. The acoustic wave formation in the sub-surface area of a crystal and in the air has been studied. The dependence of the ultrasound propagation speed in the sub-surface area of a sample on the mutual orientations of a crystal and the transient grating vector has been revealed. The contactless method for temperature estimation of the sample sub-surface layer by the acoustic-wave frequency measuring has been proposed.

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1. Introduction

A lot of advantages of the spatial-modulation spectroscopy (transient gratings, dynamic gratings) method is offered by contactless diagnostics of materials exhibiting different mechanisms of response to optical excitation. The spatial-modulation spectroscopy method is based on pulsed recording of a transient grating in a material under study. Information about the photoinduced processes is obtained by simultaneous realization of the dynamic grating readout and the use of continuous laser radiation or by separate pulses with a time delay. In this way the formed diffracted signal enables one to follow relaxation kinetics of the grating recorded.

A significant merit of the method proposed is due to the possibilities to vary the transient grating period and the wavelength of recording or

readout radiation over wide ranges. A maximal value of the diffraction efficiency of a transient grating makes it possible to calculate the light-induced change in the refractive index and nonlinear optical susceptibilities of different orders [1-3]. An analysis of the diffraction efficiency as a function of time allows for evaluation of the dynamic grating lifetime and for the calculation of various material parameters including thermal diffusivity, lifetime of free carriers in semiconductors and of trapping levels in photorefractive crystals, lifetime of the excited state for activators of laser media, and so on [4-7].

The principal objective of this work is the spatial-modulation spectroscopy method development for separation of different nonlinearity mechanisms, for kinetic and thermal characteristics of materials measurements. The studies have been performed with

photorefractive crystals of bismuth silicate and with semiconductor birefringent single crystals of ZnGeP₂.

2. The method measurement

Recording of transient gratings in semiconductor materials is caused by various nonlinearity mechanisms associated with electron transition into the conduction band and subsequent population of trapping levels, medium heating and deformation of the surface. As it takes place, different types of transient gratings may be formed at the same time. A volume or a thin grating is formed depending on the absorption factor. The pump induced refractive index change results in the formation of a phase grating, whereas the absorption factor change gives rise to an amplitude grating recording. Surface deformation of a sample leads to the relief grating formation. To separate different nonlinearity mechanisms, one can use diffraction from an additional grating, the so called homodyne [8]. In this case an additional light beam, collinear and coherent to the beam diffracted from a transient grating, is used.

Let us consider the homodyne effect taking as an example the exponentially attenuated signal $E_D(t) = E_D(0)\exp(-t/\tau)$ and the stationary field of the homodyne $E_B(t) = E_B$. Due to interference of signals diffracted from the diffraction grating and from the homodyne, the total intensity may be written as follows:

$$I_D(t) = I_B + I_D(0)\exp\left(-\frac{2t}{\tau}\right) + 2\sqrt{I_B I_D(0)}\exp\left(-\frac{t}{\tau}\right)\cos\Delta\varphi \quad (2.1)$$

where I_D is a diffraction intensity, I_B is a homodyne field intensity, τ is a lifetime of a transient grating, $\Delta\varphi$ is a phase difference between diffracted fields at the transient grating under study and at the homodyne.

As it seen from (1), the total signal represents a sum of two signals with the relaxation times $\tau/2$ and τ , their contributions

being dependent on the phase difference $\Delta\varphi$ between diffracted fields at the transient grating of interest and at the homodyne. This phase difference may be controlled by variations in spatial positions of the homodyne with respect to the recorded transient grating. To separate the desired component of the diffracted signal, it is required to record kinetics for the phase difference $\Delta\varphi$ equal to 0 and π .

$$I_{D1}(t) = I_B + I_D(0)\exp\left(-\frac{2t}{\tau}\right) + 2\sqrt{I_B I_D(0)}\exp\left(-\frac{t}{\tau}\right) \quad (2.2)$$

$$I_{D2}(t) = I_B + I_D(0)\exp\left(-\frac{2t}{\tau}\right) - 2\sqrt{I_B I_D(0)}\exp\left(-\frac{t}{\tau}\right) \quad (2.3)$$

The difference signal

$$I_{D1}(t) - I_{D2}(t) = 4\sqrt{I_B I_D(0)}\exp(-t/\tau) \quad (2.4)$$

enables one to separate the desired component with the relaxation time τ .

3. Experimental setup

A scheme of the experimental setup for the transient gratings recording is shown in Fig. 1. The transient grating excitation is realized by pulsed radiation of an yttrium aluminum garnet laser at the fundamental generation wavelength 1064 nm or at the second-harmonic wavelength 532 nm. Two beams recording the grating under study were formed by means of diffraction from grating 8. Diaphragm 10 was used to separate +1 and -1-order diffraction. The setup offers a means of probing both by pulses of the same laser with the controlled time delay 12, 13 and by radiation of continuous wave laser 17. Probing in the process of the experiment described was attained by radiation of a helium-neon laser at the wavelength 632.8 nm. The diffracted beam was recorded by photodetector 16.

FIG. 1. Schematic of experimental setup: 1 – Nd:YAG laser; 2, 3, 5, 6 – mirrors; 4, 12, 13 – prisms; 7 – light filter; 8 – diffraction grating; 9, 11 – collecting lenses; 10 – diaphragm; 14 – glass wedge; 15 – sample under study; 16 – photodetector; 17 – continuous-wave laser (helium-neon or semiconductor); 18 – shutter blind.

The experimental setup was calibrated with the use of a stain steel thermal-diffusivity standard manufactured in the form of a polished plate, officially certified at D.I. Mendeleev All-Russian Research Institute for Metrology (Saint-Petersburg). According to the certificate, thermal diffusivity of this standard is $\chi_{standard} = 0.040 \text{ cm}^2/\text{s} \pm 6\%$.

Taking this standard as a sample under study, a plot for the surface transient grating relaxation time as a function of the grating period squared was constructed using local excitation of the standard by laser radiation and by the formation of a transient grating with different values of the spatial period Λ . The calibration plot for $\tau_{standard}(\Lambda_{standard}^2)$ is given in Fig. 2. Accuracy of measurements is supported by the fact that relaxation time of a thermal transient grating is well described by the known formula $\tau = \Lambda_{standard}^2/4\pi^2\chi_{standard}$. As it seen, all experimental points of the plot over the range characteristic for the formed grating period from 15 to 70 μm fall on a straight line originating from the point (0, 0). A series of several measurements gives $\chi_{standard} = 0.044; 0.037; 0.038 \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}$, that is close to the certified value of thermal diffusivity for the standard.

Besides, a sample of standard duraluminium in the form of a 7-mm thick plate was used as a test sample. One of its sides was polished with the help of diamond turning up to the optical quality.

FIG. 2. Relaxation time of the transient grating (DG) as a function of the squared grating period

According to the reference data (for example, see [8]), this material exhibits the following parameters: density $\rho = 2.79 \text{ g/cm}^3$, heat capacity $c = 0.92 \text{ J/gK}$; the heat conductivity, being significantly dependent on the impurity content percentage, was varying as $\alpha = 1.2 - 1.3 \text{ W/cm}$ (at the thermal diffusivity $\chi = \alpha/c\rho = 0.47 - 0.51 \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}$).

FIG. 3. Kinetics of the diffraction signal kinetics on excitation of a thermal grating with the period 12.5 μm on the surface of duraluminium

Fig. 3 shows the typical kinetics recorded in experiments with the sample under study. Based on the results obtained from comparison of the measured kinetics with the theoretical dependence $(\text{Erfc})^2$ [10] (gray line of the plot), the thermal grating lifetime $\chi = \Lambda^2/4\pi^2\tau$ for the

grating period $\Lambda = 12.5 \mu\text{m}$ comes to $0.52 \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}$ in a good agreement with the reference values (an error of a few percent).

The result of measuring the thermal diffusivity χ shown in Fig. 3 corresponds to the surface layer thickness $4 \mu\text{m}$. This is associated with a depth of heat penetration, normally to the sample surface, during the lifetime of a thermal grating.

4. Recording of dynamic gratings in a crystal of bismuth silicate

Photorefractive crystals of bismuth silicate belong to broad-bandgap semiconductors. Their optical properties are greatly influenced by impurities and defects of the crystal lattice which lead to origination of donor and acceptor traps in the forbidden band [11, 12]. As it follows from the conducted experimental studies [13–16], lifetimes of trapping levels may be varying from micro- and millisecond to seconds or even hours according to the depth of their occurrence. Owing to trapping levels, one can use radiation with greater wavelengths as compared to the vertical interband transitions [11, 17]. Electron diffusion in the conduction band leads to the formation of a space-charge field and to the refractive index modulation because of the Pockels effect. One of the advantages offered by the sillenite-family (bismuth silicate and bismuth titanate) photorefractive crystals is the real-time formation of transient gratings. The possibility for constant rerecording of dynamic gratings dictates the use of bismuth silicate and titanate crystals in adaptive interferometers, holographic systems for information recording and processing [18–20].

Recording is provided by the second-harmonic radiation of a neodymium laser with the wavelength 532 nm and the pulse duration 10 ns. The experimental setup allows for variations of the period of the interference pattern forming a transient grating within the refractive crystal. Probing radiation is from a continuous-wave helium-neon laser. The diffracted beam is directed

to the photodetector and recorded by a digital oscilloscope. Fig. 4 demonstrates the obtained oscillograms.

a)

b)

c)

FIG. 4. Oscillograms of a signal diffracted from a dynamic grating with the period 400 nm in a bismuth silicate crystal at the laser radiation intensity $1 \text{ P}\mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^2$ and temporal scale a) 500 ms/div; b) 5 ms/div; c) 50 Ojs/div.

As seen in Fig. 4, the diffracted signal has two components, one of which is fast formed in a period of several hundred microseconds (Fig. 4, b). Then the formation of a long-lived grating takes about two hundred seconds (Fig. 4a). Two types of the formed gratings may be due to different trapping levels (close to the conduction band and in depth of the forbidden band).

FIG. 5. The formation (a, c) and relaxation (b, d) times of short- (a, b) and long-lived (c, d) gratings with different periods as a function of the incident radiation intensity.

To elucidate peculiarities of the formation of short- and long-lived dynamic gratings, have performed experiments with gratings of different periods. It has been found that, irrespective of the grating period, the diffracted signal reveals a fast and a slow component. Fig. 5 shows the formation and the relaxation times of short- and long-lived gratings with the periods 800 nm and 1200 nm as a function of the incident-radiation intensity. The intensity varies over the range from 100 kW/cm² to 3.5 MW/cm².

The presented plots demonstrate that the formation and relaxation times of short-lived gratings are weakly dependent on their periods but are greatly increased as the intensity of recording laser radiation increases. However, the relaxation time of a long-lived grating is practically independent of the intensity, being significantly dependent on the dynamic grating period. The revealed patterns may be explained by the local formation mechanisms of short-lived gratings and by the spatial nonlocalities in nonlinear variations of the refractive index in the case of long-lived gratings.

5. The surface properties of single-crystal ZnGeP₂ studied by the transient gratings method

The birefringent uniaxial single-crystal of ZnGeP₂ is a nonlinear medium which is used for the parametric frequency transformation of optical radiation in the mid-IR range from 3.5 to 8 microns. Also, this material looks promising for the second harmonic generation by CO and CO₂ lasers as well as for the development of terahertz-range coherent sources.

In this work, two plane-parallel polished plates, measuring 6x15 mm and 2 mm thick, have been studied by the transient grating method. In the first sample (AN-1) the optical axis C is oriented normally to its surface, whereas in the second sample (AG-2) it lies in plane of the plate. According to the method applied (schematic diagram is given in Fig.1), the samples are excited by two coherent 70-ps laser pulses at the wavelength 532 nm. Readout is provided by a helium-neon laser at a wavelength of 633 nm. Transient gratings excitation was carried out by 70-ps laser pulses at the wavelength 532 nm. The type of a recorded transient grating, its diffraction efficiency and lifetime depend on the mechanisms varying optical parameters of the crystal.

5.1. In-plane thermal diffusivity measurements

This part of the paper presents a study of the thermal diffusivity of a surface layer in the crystals. As follows from the absorption spectrum of the material controlled, the penetration depth of exciting radiation (optical thickness) at the wavelength 532 nm is no greater than 30 Ojm. For this reason all the studies were carried out in reflected light.

It has been shown experimentally that, at the surface energy-density 2.5 mJ/cm² used for sample pumping, the diffraction efficiency of a thermal grating equals (2.5-3)×10⁻⁵. Such efficiency has been obtained due to the

preliminary calibration of a recording system using a set of neutral optical filters, certified for transmission, at the wavelength of probe radiation.

From a reasonable assumption that the main contribution to the diffraction signal formation is made by a grating of the surface-relief type and using the formula for the efficiency of a grating of this type $\eta = (\pi h/\lambda)^2$, where h is the surface relief height [6], we have the initial value of h to be approximately 1 nm.

Due to a surface nature of transient grating, with the thermal gradient formed simultaneously in two directions (directed normally and along the sample surface), the recorded kinetics are approximated by means of the additional error function $\text{Erfc}(t/\tau)^{0.5}$ [22], where τ is the lifetime of a transient grating.

Fig. 6 shows the typical kinetics of the diffracted signal (a) and the grating relaxation time as a function of the period squared (b), taking the grating period Λ that equals 25 and 50 μm .

As it expected for thermal transient gratings, the relaxation time is proportional to the grating period squared. The in-plane thermal diffusivity of a sample along its surface may be estimated by means of the slope of the straight-line function $(\tau)\Lambda^2$ in Fig. 6,b. The measured lifetime of a thermal grating is $\tau=1.1$ μs for the period 25 μm (see Fig. 6a). The in-plane thermal diffusivity, calculated by the ratio, equals $(15B\pm 1.0) \times 10^{-2} \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}$.

The heat conductivity, calculated knowing the values for heat capacity and density of the material under study [21], comes to $(0.24B\pm 0.02) \text{ W}/(\text{cm}\cdot\text{K})$. The result obtained is 30% higher than the heat conductivity given in [23], is possibly due to lower concentration of the point defects which are typically present in crystals of this type and adversely affect the heat transfer efficiency. At the same time, no noticeable anisotropy of heat conductivity has been observed for different orientations of the thermal grating vector with respect to the C axis of the crystals. It is in accordance with data of [23].

FIG. 6. The typical kinetics of the diffraction signal attenuation in a ZnGeP 2 crystal (a) and the grating relaxation time as a function of the squared period (b).

5.2. Acoustic waves excitation in surface air layers

When the thermal transient grating in thin sub-surface layer is excited the effect of acoustic wave excitation may be revealed [24, 25]. Earlier this effect has been considered as a factor distorting the diffracted signal dynamics. In this section it is demonstrated that one can obtain additional information about the proceeding processes by measurements of the

parameters for an acoustic wave in the air and in the sub-surface of samples.

Fig. 7 shows the starting part of kinetics for the diffracted signal (Fig. 6, a) with higher temporal resolution. One can observe regular pulsations in the nanosecond time range. The fast Fourier-transform operation enables us to separate and to estimate frequencies of the excited ultrasound ν . The calculated values 10 and 130 MHz (Fig. 7, b) may be associated with excitation of two surface acoustic waves: in the air and in sub-surface layer of the sample under study.

Measurements of the frequencies for excited ultrasound ν with the known transient grating spatial period $\Lambda = 25$ Ojm enable one to calculate the acoustic-wave propagation velocity V as $V_{usw} = \Lambda\nu$.

Optical axis of the crystal AN-1 is normal to its surface. The transient grating vector, and hence the ultrasound propagation direction, is oriented along the surface, i.e. the crystal optical axis and the grating vector are mutually orthogonal. At the frequency of ultrasound measured in the sample $\nu = 115$ MHz, hence the calculated ultrasound velocity is $V_{usw} = 2875$ m/s. Rotation of the sample by 90° around the optical axis leads to 17% increase in the frequency and in the velocity of ultrasound propagation. So that ν and V_{usw} values are 134.2 MHz and 3350 m/s respectively.

Sample AG-2 is oriented so that its optical axis is parallel to the surface of its polished face. According to the measurements, the frequency of ultrasound is $\nu = 129.5$ MHz and the velocity of ultrasound is $V_{usw} = 3228$ m/s. Rotation of a polished surface of the sample by 90° in its plane causes no variation of the controlled parameters.

The ultrasound propagation velocity in the air was found to be about $375B \pm 5$ m/s for both samples, regardless of their orientation or the ultrasound frequency. The obtained values of the sound velocity of in a surface layer of the air were used for approximate estimation of the temperature T in the area of sample excitation. According to the reference data given in [26], the graph (shown in Fig. 8) was constructed

for velocity of sound in the air as a function of temperature $V_{usw}(T)$. Using the measured velocity of sound in the air $375B \pm 5$ m/s, the authors consider that the temperature, averaged over the aperture and depth of the grating at the moment of its excitation, is approximately 340-350 K.

Based on the fact that an optical thickness of the excited layer in the sample is of the order of 20–30 Ojm, i.e. comparable to the acoustic wave length, it is assumed that a surface acoustic wave in a sample is formed. By studying the velocity of ultrasound as a function of its frequency one can determine a value of the Young modulus in the boundary layer of the sample and to estimate the mechanical properties of the material under study [27, 28].

5.3. Amplitude and phase components of diffraction from complex transient grating

Transient gratings may be formed due to variations both in the absorption factor and the refractive index or due to changes in the surface relief. When the absorption factor changes, we deal with amplitude gratings, whereas in the case of changing refractive index or relief we have phase gratings. It is well known that in a case of complex (amplitude-phase) grating, the diffracted signal has two components, phase-shifted relative each other by $\pi/2$. Analysis of the diffracted signal has been performed using for measurements an additional grating homodyne [8], described in Section 2. A role of the homodyne is governed by its ability to amplify or attenuate the intensity of diffraction depending on the phase difference of signals diffracted from a transient grating or from the homodyne, $\Delta\varphi$, in accordance with formula (1). Considering the phase difference of signals diffracted from the amplitude and the phase grating, homodyne makes it possible to observe separately the amplitude or the phase component of the studied grating. Indeed, when the selected phase difference between the fields of homodyne and of diffraction is $\Delta\varphi = \pi/2$, the amplified and

FIG. 7. (a) Starting part of the kinetics from Fig. 6, a and (b) a Fourier-transform spectrum for the diffraction signal, where 1 - air, 2 - surface acoustic wave

FIG. 8. Temperature dependence of the ultrasound velocity in the air layer that is in contact with the absorbing surface. ■ - reference points [26].

observed signal is from the amplitude-type surface grating. When $\Delta\varphi = 0$ or π the recorded signal is from the phase grating. Such a physical pattern is described in [29].

In the case of interest the amplitude-phase grating is formed on the surface of ZnGeP_2 crystal because the reflection factor of a probe beam depends on the intensity, for example, due to temperature increase or due to the formation

of free-carrier plasma in the surface area of the sample. Fig. 9 demonstrates the result of transition from recording the phase grating to the amplitude-type grating by selection of the phase difference between the diffraction field and the homodyne field, that equals 0 or $\pi/2$. It is seen that a slow component of the diffracted signal is due to the phase grating, and a fast component due to the amplitude one. Fig. 10 shows the attenuation kinetics of the surface amplitude grating and its exponential approximation.

Based on the comparative experimental studies with two periods of a transient grating, 25 and 50 μm , it has been found that the lifetime of the amplitude grating is independent of its period. It has been concluded that a relaxation mechanism along the grating vector is not of the diffusion type, being rather associated with the surface recombination of free carriers (fast in comparison to the phase grating) or with heat transfer in the direction normal to the surface.

6. Conclusion

The results presented demonstrate prospects of contactless potentialities of using the transient grating method for nondestructive diagnostics

FIG. 9. Starting fragments of the phase-grating attenuation kinetics obtained when the phase shift between the diffraction and homodyne fields is $\Delta\varphi = 0$ (1) or π (2), and the same for the amplitude-type grating at $\Delta\varphi = \pm\pi/2$ (3) and (4).

FIG. 10. Kinetics of the surface amplitude-grating attenuation in a nonlinear crystal of ZnGeP_2 . A solid line gives the exponential approximation with the lifetime $\tau = 15$ ns.

of materials, separation of different nonlinearity mechanisms and measurements of the thermo-optical and kinetic characteristics. With the use of pulsed dynamic grating recording in photorefractive crystals, the conditions for the development of the two formation mechanisms, which result in the formation of gratings whose lifetimes differ by five orders of magnitude (hundred of microseconds and seconds), have been determined. It has been shown that the formation

and relaxation times of short-lived gratings are weakly dependent on their periods but they are greatly increased with an increase in the intensity of laser radiation recording a transient grating. Relaxation time of a long-lived grating is practically independent of the intensity, being significantly dependent on the transient grating period. The obtained results point to the fact that recording mechanism of short-lived gratings is local, whereas the formation of long-lived gratings is realized by a nonlocal (diffusion) mechanism.

In the process of recording the surface transient gratings in monocrystals ZnGeP_2 the amplitude and the phase components of the diffracted signal have been separated. It has been detected experimentally that attenuation of a signal diffracted from the amplitude grating is due to relaxation processes of the local type, for example, by recombination of free charge carriers.

It has been found experimentally that the in-plane thermal diffusivity equals $15 \times 10^{-2} \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}$ and it has been calculated that the heat conductivity of single crystal ZnGeP_2 is 0.24 W/cm . It has been established that there is no anisotropy of heat conductivity in a single crystal of ZnGeP_2 for different orientations of the thermal grating vector with respect to the

crystal axis. Of particular interest is the formation of an acoustic wave in the surface area of the crystal and in the air. It has been revealed that the ultrasound propagation speed in the surface area of a sample is significantly dependent on the mutual orientations of the crystal and of the transient grating vector. The method to measure the local temperature by the measured frequency of an acoustic wave and the calculated acoustic speed has been also proposed.

It is expedient to use the presented results in optical material science: on contactless testing of nonlinear-optical and laser materials

by the relevant parameters which include the allowed in-depth thermal diffusivity and its anisotropy, mechanical properties, photoinduced surface effects.

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